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Development of Engineering Education Through Better Understanding of the Students' Values

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INTRODUCTION

Values guide our actions. Therefore it is critical to understand the values of engineering students if we wish to understand their behavior, choices and actions. Understanding the values of students has a huge potential in developing higher education in many aspects: developing the content of the engineering studies, guiding

the selection of field of science matching personal needs, motivating and committing to studies, and many more possible applications.

Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland (TEK) has conducted research on the values of Finnish academic engineering students in 2017. The research is based on Shalom Schwartz's Theory of Basic Human Values which is a highly validated theory for intercultural research. The research was conducted as a part of TEK's annual Student Survey with approximately 2300 respondents.

The results of the research are categorized by field of study which provides interesting insights on the differences in values between different engineering studies. The results of the overall academic engineering students are also compared to the general Finnish values researched on a national scale. Compared to average Finnish values the engineering students value work morale related values very highly and value traditions much less than the average Finnish person. Notable differences can also be found when comparing different fields of science in academic engineering studies. For example all fields of science value either Benevolence, Universalism or Work highest except for architects whom value Self-Direction highest. The results provide a foundation to which conclusions and development suggestions for developing engineering education can be based on.

1 SCHWARTZ'S THEORY OF BASIC HUMAN VALUES

Values are important to understand because they strongly guide our actions. The methodology of the research is based on Shalom Schwartz's theory of basic human values. The theory is a well-validated tool for measuring values and comparing the values of different cultures internationally. The theory is used for example in the European Social Survey to compare the values of European citizens in different countries. [1] [2]

The 11 value types in this research are the following. The first 10 values are a part of the Schwartz value theorem and the last one, work, is a value defined by Finnish professor emeritus Klaus Helkama. The Schwartz value theorem only accounts for value types that are accountable in every major culture whereas the Work value has not been validated in intercultural research. However work as a value has been studied in Finnish context so it is justified to include it in this country-specific comparison of values. [1] [2] [3]

- **Benevolence.** Defining goal: preserving and enhancing the welfare of those with whom one is in frequent personal contact (the 'in-group').
- **Universalism.** Defining goal: understanding, appreciation, tolerance, and protection for the welfare of *all* people and for nature.
- **Achievement.** Defining goal: personal success through demonstrating competence according to social standards.
- **Self-Direction.** Defining goal: independent thought and action--choosing, creating, exploring.
- **Stimulation.** Defining goal: excitement, novelty, and challenge in life.

- **Hedonism.** Defining goal: pleasure or sensuous gratification for oneself.
- **Power.** Defining goal: social status and prestige, control or dominance over people and resources.
- **Security.** Defining goal: safety, harmony, and stability of society, of relationships, and of self.
- **Conformity.** Defining goal: restraint of actions, inclinations, and impulses likely to upset or harm others and violate social expectations or norms.
- **Tradition.** Defining goal: respect, commitment, and acceptance of the customs and ideas that one's culture or religion provides.
- **Work** (*not used in the Schwartz value theorem*). Defining goal: diligence, rigour, systematic, perseverance and thrift.

The above-mentioned 11 values project a two-dimensional coordinate system (Fig. 1) in which one axis represents the Conservation – Openness to Change dimension and the other axis represents the Self-Transcendence – Self-Enhancement dimension. [5]

Fig. 1. The structure of the different value types not including the Finnish context value of Work. [5]

The values located close to each other in Fig. 1 are highly compatible with each other and vice versa. The Work value is missing from the value circle as it only includes the interculturably comparable values. [1] [2]

The values are measured by one or more questions on how the respondent relates to the value in question. For example the European Social Survey (ESS) uses a 21-question survey for the 10 interculturably comparable values whereas the Schwartz Value Survey (SVS) developed by Schwartz has a total of 57 questions. The respondents in the ESS weight how much the described person in each claim is or is not like the respondent. The evaluation is done in different scales in different surveys,

for example the SVS uses a scale of -1 to 7 and the ESS uses a scale of 1 to 7. The values are usually presented as a prioritized list. [1] [2] [3]

2 RESEARCH

The research was conducted by Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland TEK as a part of an annual Student Survey. The Annual survey studies the employment situation of students and in 2017 it had an altering other theme which focused on values. The survey was sent to 15 000 of TEK's about 20 000 student members. The response rate of the survey was 17 % with a total of 2526 respondents. [6]

For the values research TEK used a 21-question survey also used in the European Social Survey to monitor the 10 value types in the Schwartz value theory. In addition the survey also included two more questions relating to work as a value for which the questions have been developed by professor emeritus Klaus Helkama from the University of Helsinki. [4] [7]

The values of Finnish population has also been widely studied and the value profile of average Finnish respondents will be used as a comparison to point out how the students of engineering and technology differ from an average Finn. [4]

3 RESULTS

There are many ways in which we could present and examine the data, for example by age, by gender etc. We concluded to present the differences between different fields of sciences to highlight how similar most students of engineering and technology are based on their values. There are however also major differences which are also very interesting. The student population in the fields of engineering and technology will also be compared to an average Finnish value profile to point out the main differences that the students in technology have in the context of Finnish population.

The value research is usually presented as a prioritized list as it is also done in this paper. The comparison between Finnish population and academic engineering student population value profiles is presented in Table 1. The table also includes comparison of value priorities between different fields of science.

Table 1. The priority of values comparison between average Finnish people and Finnish M.Sc.(Tech) students.

	Benevolence	Universalism	Work	Self- Direction	Hedonism	Security	Achievement	Conformity	Stimulation	Tradition	Power
FINNISH M.SC(TECH) STUDENTS AVERAGE N=2076	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
FINNISH POPULATION AVERAGE N=1652	2	1	7	4	7	3	10	5	9	6	11
MECHANICAL & ENERGY ENGINEERING N=358	2	3	1	4	5	6	8	7	9	10	11
ELECTRICAL & AUTOMATION ENGINEERING N=485	1	3	2	4	5	6	8	7	9	10	11
INFORMATION & TELECOMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY N=270	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	7	10	9	11
PROCESS & MATERIALS ENGINEERING N=363	1	2	3	5	4	6	7	8	9	10	11
BUILDING CONSTRUCTION & SURVEYING TECHNOLOGY N=119	1	3	2	6	4	5	7	8	9	10	11
INDUSTRIAL MANAGEMENT N=222	1	2	3	5	4	8	6	9	7	11	10
ARCHITECTURE N=59	3	2	4	1	5	6	7	9	8	11	10

A couple of things should be noted when comparing the values of an average Finn to an average academic engineering student. First of all, the Self-Transcendence and Conservation type of values generally tend to be emphasized more as people get older. As the student population is very young of age compared to the average Finnish person, it is very natural for the Openness to Change types of values to stand out. The highest priority of the Self-Transcendence values Benevolence, Universalism and Work is however not what is expected of such young respondents. These values translate to the students being very hard-working, unselfish people who want good things for all people, nature and environment more than for themselves. [8]

Fig. 2. The priority of values comparison between different fields of science in academic engineering studies

The values of the Finnish M.Sc.(Tech) students is quite similar between different fields of science. The biggest difference is seen on Architecture students whom value Self-Direction over all else whereas most of the students valued Benevolence the highest.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Since values dictate our actions, the research has huge potential in many aspects, including developing engineering education. We will point out a few applications but the list is in no way complete.

4.1 Student marketing

Understanding what kind of value profiles the potential applicants have has a huge potential in proper marketing for the target group. Since the benevolence and universalism are the top two values of engineering students, engineering education should be especially promoted on how it can help both humankind and save nature which are aspects included in the two values.

4.2 Developing engineering education

The value profiles of the engineering students give great insight on how the contents of the engineering studies could be further developed to match the interests and sources of motivation of the students. Students are often demanding more concrete examples on how the heavily theoretical studies are actually related to solutions in our everyday life. As the students value benevolence and universalism over other values, the study contents should be made concrete by how the studies relate to creating a better world.

The universalism aspect also includes a value "respect for nature" which implies that also the environmental aspects should be highlighted for students to be more motivated to the subject. After all, all of the engineering studies are strongly related to solutions that can contribute to the well-being of people, nature and general happiness of mankind. To name a few examples on how technology plays a key role in preserving nature and improves the well-being of humans: a stable and secure power supply enables hospitals to save more lives, the use of renewable energy sources reduce pollution and climate change, and autonomous vehicles can reduce the energy consumption in logistics sector. None of these solutions are possible without engineering expertise, but these kind of viewpoints in the importance of technology for general well-being is often neglected in engineering education.

REFERENCES

- [1] Helkama, K. (2015). Suomalaisten arvot – mikä meille oikeasti on tärkeää?, Suomalaisen kirjallisuuden seura, Helsinki, pp. 80-111.

- [2] Schwartz, S.H. (2007). ESS Core Questionnaire Human Values. A Proposal for Measuring Value Orientations across Nations. Available online: http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/docs/methodology/core_ess_questionnaire/ESS_core_questionnaire_human_values.pdf

- [3] Schwartz, S. H. (2012). An Overview of the Schwartz Theory of Basic Values. Online Readings in Psychology and Culture, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1116>

- [4] Helkama, K. (2015). Suomalaisten arvot – mikä meille oikeasti on tärkeää?, Suomalaisen kirjallisuuden seura, Helsinki, pp. 238-243

- [5] Karppinen H., Korhonen M. (2013). Do forest owners share the public's values? An application of Schwartz's value theory. *Silva Fennica* vol. 47 no. 1 article id 894. <https://doi.org/10.14214/sf.894>
- [6] Tekniikan akateemiset TEK. Opiskelijatutkimus 2017. Available online: <https://www.tek.fi/fi/uutishuone/tutkimukset/opiskelijatutkimus>
- [7] ESS Human Values Scale. Computing Scores for the 10 Human values. Available online: http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/docs/methodology/ESS1_human_values_scale.pdf
- [8] Helkama, K. (2015). Suomalaisten arvot – mikä meille oikeasti on tärkeää?, Suomalaisen kirjallisuuden seura, Helsinki, pp. 203-237.